

Geospatial Analysis of Agricultural Soil Suitability in Mainland Portugal

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Abstract. This study examines the spatial distribution of key soil health indicators—pH (of CaCl_2 and H_2O), electrical conductivity (EC), and organic carbon (OC) in Portugal. Spatial interpolation methods, namely Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) and Empirical Bayesian Kriging (EBK), were utilized to analyse soil properties. EBK outperformed IDW in accuracy and spatial coherence, making it more reflective of gradual changes in soil properties. A weighted map of soil health indicators identified the central and southern regions of Portugal as the most agriculturally suitable. This study highlights spatial statistics as a valuable tool for targeted soil management and demonstrates a scalable and reproducible framework using globally recognized soil health metrics.

Submission Type. Analysis

BoK Concepts. [AM7] Spatial statistics, [TA12] EO for societal and environmental challenges

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1 Introduction

Soil quality indicators, including pH measured in CaCl_2 ($\text{pH}_{\text{CaCl}_2}$) and H_2O ($\text{pH}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$), electrical conductivity (EC), and organic carbon (OC) are vital for evaluating agricultural suitability. Soil pH regulates nutrient availability (Butnan, Sriraj and Toomsan, 2023), EC indicates salinity that impact crop yield (Ramos, Gonçalves and Van Genuchten, 2024) and OC enhances

fertility (Shen *et al.*, 2024). However, agricultural potential in Portugal is increasingly threatened by unsustainable practices, urbanization, and salinization, which degrade soil health (Lal, 2004; Ramos, Gonçalves and Van Genuchten, 2024).

The analysis mapped soil health indicators using IDW and EBK to visualize spatial variability and identify regions with optimal agricultural potential. This study demonstrates the integration of spatial interpolation at a national scale in Portugal, offering a reproducible, crop-independent approach for identifying agriculturally favourable areas based on fundamental soil health indicators.

2 Methods

This study focuses on mainland Portugal, characterized by coastal plains and mountainous terrains, with a Mediterranean climate in the south and a temperate maritime climate in the north.

2.1 Data and Software Availability

This study utilized the LUCAS 2018 TOPSOIL dataset¹. Land Use Land Cover (LULC) data was derived from Sentinel-2 imagery (2018) using ArcGIS Pro's built-in atlas.

Exploratory spatial and statistical analyses, including IDW and EBK, were conducted using ArcGIS Pro 3.3. The weighted overlay was executed via the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) Priority Calculator² developed by Goepel (2018). No code was developed for this study.

¹ The LUCAS 2018 TOPSOIL dataset is available upon request at <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/lucas-2018-topsoil-data>.

² The AHP Priority Calculator is available at <https://bpmsg.com/ahp/ahp-calc.php> and is documented in <https://doi.org/10.13033/ijahp.v10i3.590>.

2.2 Workflow

The methodology is summarized in Figure 1. Soil data was filtered to cropland-specific points. Descriptive statistics and Pearson's correlations were used to assess variability and relationships among indicators.

Figure 1. Process flowchart.

Spatial variability was visualized using Voronoi maps, while Global Moran's I analyses assessed spatial autocorrelation. Soil property surfaces were generated using IDW and EBK and compared via error statistics from cross-validation results. EBK was optimized using uniform settings (subset size: 200, transformation: log-empirical, neighbourhood: 10–15) across all indicators.

AHP was used to assign weights for the weighted overlay analysis, utilising the optimal indicator ranges for most crops and soil types summarized in Table 1. The final map was refined by excluding urban areas with LULC data.

Table 1. Optimal values per indicator.

Indicator	Optimal Range	References
pH _{CaCl₂}	5.5 - 6.8	(FAO, 2021)
pH _{H₂O}	6.0 - 7.5	(FAO, 2021; NRCS, 2011)
EC	< 200 mS/m, lower is preferable	(NRCS, 2011; Ramos, Gonçalves and Van Genuchten, 2024) (NRCS, 2011)
OC	≥ 100 g/kg (10%); higher is preferable	(Prout <i>et al.</i> , 2021; Zdruli, Jones and Montanarella)

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Descriptive Statistics and Correlations

Soil pH in both CaCl (pH_{CaCl₂}) and H₂O (pH_{H₂O}) shows moderate variability, with averages indicating slightly acidic to neutral conditions suitable for most crops. EC has a high coefficient of variation, suggesting significant spatial salinity variability. OC exhibits wide variability with a positively skewed distribution, indicating a few

locations with exceptionally high values that strongly influence soil fertility.

Pearson's correlations indicated a strong positive relationship between pH_{CaCl₂} and pH_{H₂O} ($r = 0.97$). However, they were separately treated in the analysis due to subtle differences in ranges, which indicate distinct chemical responses. Weak correlations were observed between all the other variables, reflecting their independent contributions to soil health.

3.2 Spatial Patterns

Voronoi maps (Figure 2) showed that northern regions had widespread acidity, while central and southern regions exhibited more favourable pH levels. EC was generally low but shows higher variability in the western and southern regions. OC concentrations peaked in the south, indicating better fertility. The Global Moran's I confirmed significant spatial autocorrelation for all indicators (p -value < 0.05).

Figure 2. Bivariate Voronoi maps of indicators.

3.3 Interpolation Accuracy

Cross-validation confirmed the superior performance of EBK over IDW (Table 2). Both surfaces show consistent overall spatial trends, such as northern acidity and southern fertility hotspots, but EBK produced smoother transitions as it accounts for spatial uncertainty, better

reflecting the gradual soil property changes in space (Figure 3).

Table 2. Cross-validation metrics for IDW and EBK.

	Mean Absolute Error (MAE)		Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	
	IDW	EBK	IDW	EBK
pH _{CaCl2}	0.0016	0.0056	0.7354	0.7006
pH _{H2O}	0.0042	0.0060	0.7603	0.7206
EC	0.1312	0.1748	6.2346	0.9907
OC	0.5302	0.3636	14.4586	13.6856

Figure 3. EBK-interpolated surfaces of indicators.

3.4 Soil Suitability Mapping

AHP assigned weights of 49.3%, 31.1%, and 19.6% to pH, EC, and OC, respectively, reflecting their contributions to the suitability index and aligning with the agricultural productivity framework by Rukhsana and Molla (2023). The weighted overlay analysis in Figure 4 identified central and southern Portugal as the most suitable for agriculture, while northern areas, characterized by acidic soils, showed lower suitability. Urban areas were excluded for a more realistic evaluation.

Figure 4. Final weighted suitability map.

4 Conclusion

This study assessed soil agricultural suitability across mainland Portugal using pH_{CaCl2}, pH_{H2O}, EC, and OC as key indicators. EBK outperformed IDW in producing reliable soil property maps. AHP emphasized the dominant influence of pH, followed by EC and OC, in forming the suitability index. The results identified central and southeastern Portugal as the most suitable regions for agriculture, while northern areas were limited by acidic soils. These findings can identify suitable areas for agricultural production and inform targeted interventions for soil management and land-use planning.

The four indicators used in this study are globally recognized soil health metrics, making the framework easily adaptable and scalable to other regions with similar data availability. Future studies could enhance the approach by incorporating crop-specific requirements,

climate variables, and socio-economic factors such as market access and labour availability.

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The authors declare AI tools were utilized for language editing but not for generating scientific content, research data, or substantive conclusions. All intellectual and creative work, including the analysis and interpretation of data, is original and has been conducted by the authors without AI assistance.

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Author contribution.

Margaux Elijah Neri: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization

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Sara Ribeiro: Writing – review & editing, Supervision

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